

Sango Religious group in Oyo

Data source: Personal Expertise

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* Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.

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Oyo people are one of the indigenous religious society among the Yoruba race in Oyo state, Nigeria. Their population is about 471,000. They speak Oyo dialect of Yoruba version language. The people once an empire came into limelight around fifteen centuries. From oral history, the town was founded by Oranmiyan the last son of Oduduwa, the great ancestor of the Yoruba people. The religious and political existence of the people have the traces of migration linked with Ife origin due to common ancestral genealogy shared by all other Yoruba cities. They have a ritual tradition which is spectacular but attached to Sango festival and oya festival. Oya was the wife of sango during his life time. They showcased this festival with Bata drum and it makes it distinct for ritual practices. Sango is recognized as the spirit of thunder and lightning; he became the king of Oyo around sixteen centuries. He was known to be an historical figure with strange and unpredictable character. Their indigenous religion is known as Isese (Yoruba: Ìṣẹ̀ṣẹ) and is still practiced by a number of Yoruba people. It has also been incorporated into new religious traditions throughout the African diaspora. Oyo people developed customs such as brotherhood, the ruling of Alaafins, traditional art, drumming, spiritual dances and they speak Yoruba language like other tribes. Their belief and heritage make them distinct from another tribe. They have a unique talent in drawing and sculpturing. the Oyo Empire's cultural heritage requires explaining spiritual dances and masquerades' origins, as their philosophy is different from the modern. The religious practices of the Oyo people have a diffused system in which the orisas are considered as the messenger of divine creator. There is an understanding of nature and spirits in the template of their spirituality and religiosity. This explain more better their ethical devises in which makes man responsible and thus adhere to the maintenance of golden rule of law (law of karma) guided by nature as a paramount claim in human justice and socio communal relationship. The role and depth of Oyo's influence in nurturing a Yoruba identity and consciousness among the Yoruba has continued to resonate across generations and boundaries. The Yoruba who today are found in the Southwestern part of Nigeria, the Republics of Benin and Togo, Brazil, Cuba, Trinidad and other places in the Caribbean have continued to imagine the glory and renown of the empire and the consciousness created by the Oyo and its Alaafins. Oyo has continued to live on in the lives, arts and the socio-cultural, economic and political arrangements prevalent among the Yoruba people, their neighbors and the African Diaspora The date picked for this study is determined by the development that occurred in Yoruba land within the period.1800 was the beginning of the disruption caused by the Fulani Muslim jihadist all over Yoruba kingdom and Oyo Empire. It is then important to see if the disruption in any way affects the religious tradition of the oyo people till 1900 before modern independence.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 1900 CE

Region: Oyo

Region tags: Africa, Nigeria, Oyo state

This is a map of Oyo City in Oyo State in Nigeria, West Africa. Most Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria, while Muslims tend to live in northern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ayo Salami, (2008) Yoruba Theology and Tradition: The Worship, NIDD Publishing company, Lagos
- Source 2: Dayo Ologundudu, (2008) The cradle of Yoruba Culture, Centre for Spoken Words/Institute of Yoruba Culture, U.S.A.
- Source 3: Samuel Johnson (1976) The History of the Yorubas, Lagos, C.M.S

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: www.BillSummers.net/shop.html - assessed
- Source 1 Description: www.blacfoundation.org/eguugun.pdf accessed
- Source 2 URL: ifa-houseofwisdom.com/forum/index.php?topic=5.ojwap2
- Source 2 Description: Adegbite, A, The drum and its Role in Yoruba Religion in Journal of Religion in Africa, Bricc, Vol.18, FASC1, 1988:15-26, URL: <http://www.jstor.org>
- Source 3 URL: Bankole, A., The Yoruba Master Drummer in African Arts, UCLA James S. Coleman Studies Centre, Vol.8.No 2, 1975:48-56,77-78 URL: <http://www.jstor.org>
- Source 3 Description: Kwaku Ayim Atta-Asiedu, African Traditionla Religions in Transition: The Influence of Modernism and Globalization on African Indigenous faiths ,<http://www.reserchgate.net/publication>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://premium-papers.com> ›
- Source 1 Description: The narrative here shows the cultural practices of Oyo people, their religion and the traditions believe in which Oyo was founded
- Source 2 URL: <https://fatherlandgazette.com/the-bata-drum/>
- Source 2 Description: The drum has been said to have existed for over 5 centuries and has been significant to the religious practices of the Oyo people. It identified the purposes of traditional belief system of the group. A version of history says that Sango performed his rituals while listening to the beats of the Bata drum. This is the reason most Sango plays and stories have the Bata drum played.
- Source 3 URL: Elements Of Cultural Culture In OYO - 1141 Words Bartleby.com <https://www.bartleby.com/essay/Elements-Of-Cultu>
- Source 3 Description: This is a page that documented the concepts of heritage and legacy of Oyo from the past till present. It discussed a figurative story of Oyo in symbolic manner

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: They are not competitive because they share common ancestral origin. They are united through the same mythology.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Children newly born in families of devotees of this deity are made to undergo the rites of passage. This confers membership of the group on them.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership of the group increases as lay people seek spiritual assistance from the priests of the religious group. When they record very positive results from such consultations, some of them decide to join the group so their gains could be consolidated.

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: The Royal families belong to this religious group. The deity - a deified ancestor - was once a notable king in the old Oyo kingdom.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Through rite of passage of the group, you're a member

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: by initiation or divine encounter

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: This could happen through divine encounter or experience of individual outside the group or spiritual consultation availed interested individuals outside the cult group.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: But they enjoy benefits like sponsorship during their festival and other religious activities

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage to their holy land and yearly festival known as isese are sponsored by the government in some cases.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: The group exist in a pluralistic society. So, observance to religious practices is by right.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 20000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2

Notes: The percentage were small because they lack modern technique required for acquiring members

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: They relied on oral sources that are passed from one generation to the other. The oral sources like proverbs, dance and songs, liturgy and rituals, invocations and prayer, art works, myths, systematic recitals constitute the scriptures of this group. Yoruba oral traditions confined the emergence of Bata message to religious ritual, its voice and language serve as accompaniment to Egungun (Masquerade) and Sango (god of thunder) during their life time. The drum message in this context is an encyclopaedia of traditional philosophy such as proverbs, wise saying, riddles and myths that are express through puns and figure of speech.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: since it is not documented nor systematic then it is subject to alteration.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual specialist are the only people that transmit.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: There is religious ground where sango festival holds every year and there is shrine where worship take place.

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: Tombs are displayed since the death of any religious leader is meant to be sacred

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: There are no special cemeteries because adherent are buried like every other human

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Shrines where the deity is venerated is situated close to the town

↳ Altars:

– No

Notes: There is a major joint altar for all indigenous religious groups in the community. This altar serves all adherents of the different orisas (deities) together. There is a specific day for this ecumenism of indigenous religious worship.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Notes: This is relative in some cases.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Pictures already uploaded

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space

Notes: yes. the attached is an evidence

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: sango is represented in the act of fire. This more reason magic of fire must be done during festival

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: There is the belief in ancestral veneration. Every decease are considered as ancestor.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The group possesses Seere Sango (Gourd rattle) Ose Sango (Sango's wand) These can be seen with the Sango priest in the picture below.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: sango and baba mogba(the spiritual elder) are the human icons that represent the image of worship.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: costumes, thunderbolts(edun ara), Gourd rattle (sango's wand),Ose sango(magical wand of sango)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The deity of this religious group died in a bush now considered to be sacred and thus isolated with a fence around the spot. The group thereafter settled there and became farmers.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: There is a yearly festival which brings people from far and near. The occasion of the yearly Sango festival is exploited by some devotees and tourists to embark on a pilgrimage to the significant religious site of the deity. This offers attendees the opportunity to visit Sango shrine for prayers and other spiritual activities. The Elegun Sango and the spiritual fathers known as Mogba are always available to attend to people who attend the festival for various reasons.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Sango the ancestors' designate of the religion was considered to have died through hanging but

this fact could not be established as various arguments were held for this.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: There is a cult of ancestors which the culture of the people identified as the abode of the living dead. This abode is a migration from the earthly world to the realm of the spirits where kinsmen other relatives left in the earthly world are meant to be monitored. This is a degree of prestige for old kinsmen that fulfilled the conditions and requirements attached to the entrance.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Realm of the ancestors

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: The reincarnation in this system is cyclical. Human are meant to be reborn into this world for compensation of every good deeds offered during their first survival in the world.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Those that behaved adversely on their first existence in the world are meant to be punished. They are therefore returned or incarnated as inanimate object or animal.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

Notes: This is a form of punishment for those who were considered as evil folks in their first existence. They are therefore returned to the world as inanimate objects.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: A kind of rebirth in the form or resemblance of a deceased person is an example of corporate rebirth acknowledged among the Yoruba people. This cuts across several lineages and tribes in Africa.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: Abiku (a child that was born, lives for a short period and dies again. Such a child later get born again by its pervious mother through another birth).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: This is done through a special ritual because it is part of the rites of passage within the religious tradition.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: If the deceased happen to be an initiate and as well advanced in age, the lying in state would be done vertically . But , if not an initiate and just a devotee the normal horizontal lying would be done.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: There is a secondary burial where both initiate and general devotee converge for funeral service. Apart from this the primary burial arrangement are done in private with important rituals on the corpse.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

- Yes [specify]: It takes seven days for the burial to be concluded and through out the seven days, eating, drinking, and dancing round the community would be engaged with much resources expended.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Sheep, corks and pigeons are offered as sacrifice at the grave of the deceased.

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: The family makes preparations for where their deceased will be buried.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: The gods or the deities represent the supreme god in this category. Here the spirit of the ancestors or the deities like sango or oya who were considered lesser in status are representative of the Supreme God.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: There is always the impression that the ancestral spirits are present during the burial.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: These are the ancestors who are believed to have only changed address through the phenomena of death. They are however considered as living around the members of their earthly families. Ancestors are the departed spirits of the forefathers.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: They are not restricted because they are engaged in human social affairs in terms of ,religion, ethical and judicial activities . They reward and at the same time punish.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: They serve as the representative of the supreme deity many times

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The philosophy of the Yoruba is that spirits are ubiquitous . This means spirits are everywhere. This position is the case here.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: This is referred to as philosophy of knowledge of consanguinity in which the fact of being descended from the same ancestor is represented. This indicates that no one has the mind of his or her own.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: That is why most ancestors are rewarded through the birth of like figure like them. This indicates that such ancestor had done well in the previous life which he or she lived.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This makes the ideology of spiritual supplication among the Yoruba a sacred one. Before any social engagement like getting wife or husband, taking new job, the spirits must be consulted to identify what the future hold

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: The ancestors are considered to play ethical, moral, social and religious roles within the community. Eschatologically, there is the belief that the ancestors can reward and at the same time punish people here and beyond.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: They are agents assigned by the supernatural being to reward humans for their deeds in the flesh.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: their people look unto them for blessing and guidance when considering a new challenge. They also guard the family tradition and life.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They detest ill manners that makes the world complicated and thus place judgement on anyone who is being recalcitrant.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Consultations are made through divination to confirm their wishes in kind and otherwise.
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: Through dreams, vision and possession. In certain cases maiden votaries are possessed to deliver the messages of the supernatural being to the religious community.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: there is always the belief that the the ancestral spirits are present during burial
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: They are saddled with divine functions guided by their ritualized mandate. In this way they have the feeling of the gods and man. In a way they act in the position of an umpire.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The ancestors are considered to play ethical, moral, social and religious roles within the community. Eschatologically, there is the belief that the ancestors can reward and at the same time punish people here and beyond

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They have the knowledge that this world is not balance

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

Notes: their people look unto them for blessing and guidance when considering a new challenge. They also guard the family tradition and life.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

Notes: they detest ill manners that makes the world complicated and thus place judgement on any recalcitrant.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: through magic they can influence the world

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: they can scold and at the same time encourage people

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: dream, vision and possession

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: In any family spirit of the ancestors are paramount and equal. The Yoruba people like Oyo strongly believe that the departed ancestors do reincarnate and also be born as a grandchild of the departed parents. The model is the same.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: Although beings are restricted through their environmental domain, but their actions are not limited to their domain when it comes to the duty of embarking on rescue missions on behalf of their children and loved ones.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: The structure of the supernatural world is as follows: supreme being-divinities-spirits-ancestors. It is a pantheon of organized religious structure through which worshippers network their supplications to the invisible world. This structure is referred to as diffused monotheism.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are guardians of morality. they are the custodians of laws and customs of the societies. The ancestors may punish those who disobey the norms of the society.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: food like deer and, Rattus must not be provided during sango worship so as not incur its wrath.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The premises where rituals will be celebrated to Sango are solely sacred and only the members of the esoteric group are granted access. Those who are non officiate of the cult should not get into the arena.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Red colour is symbolic to Sango. It is a taboo to use any other colour for his ritual.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: There is understanding of procreation which help membership extension. Adherents can marry more than one wife for family membership to grow.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: It is noted that when Sango indicates his acceptance of the offering during his festival, the participant dance around returning to eat and drink. all of the meat offered to sango is then removed and eaten by by members of the group. anyone who has been involved in wrong doing should not eat this meat, if wrongdoer does, such people will die. This is an indication that you must not lie.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In oya festival witnessing the sacred fire is tantamount to honoring oath of allegiance. This means for such who witnessed will make the next festival.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Notes: Magic is an act of sorcery. During Sango festival this act is permissible for spiritual edification of members

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Ethically the group adheres to the civil requirements of becoming an ancestor. These requirements include the fact that the individuals considered: must have died well, must have lived well, have attained a ripe full old age, must have left behind good children and must have received a decent burial. So disobeying elders will not make them fulfil the requirements. In addition, the children must be well trained.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: They believe that is the only way human sanctity can be achieved. It is a way of ensuring spiritual cleansing of the members of the society.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: They adhere to this because it goes with mandates of peace and harmony which establish or fulfil cooperation and interplay between sacred and non-sacred.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The group considers mutual trust as a core aim of development.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: There are natural punishments for any one who constitutes nuisance within the public domain. Thieves and evildoers are punished through natural disasters like thunder strike.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: punishments in this regard are meted by Sango god of thunder by striking the offender with lightning.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Due to ritual effect of punishment, the effect may occur impersonally.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: With effects of ritual or sacrifice for natural punishment, law of karma may prevail.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The reasons for the punishment is to forestall societal peace in order to avoid social and natural disaster that may arise. sometimes it is consider to be an atonement.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- No

Notes: General social norms are not prescribed by the religious group. Other modern civil agents also play a major role.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Yes

Notes: To the group fundamental principle of justice is equality, reciprocity or equivalence between individuals. this is the understanding of the consciousness of justice and fair play.

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
 - Present and clear

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

- I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: This is essential when ritual processes is on. It provides sacredness between the holy and the profane.

Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Male can marry more than one wife. It is a required norm in their tradition

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Female can only be married to one husband as this is ethically approved.

Other sexual constraints (males):

– I don't know

Other sexual constraints (females):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: fasting is a medium of exercising spiritual obligation and isolation from profane action.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Generally the group must abstain from jute leaves soup (ewedu), This soup is a traditional

delicacy among the yoruba people.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group forbids lawlessness and resist it with all passion, . members are therefore guided by the group correctional rules for decorum and society stability.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: There are family rituals linked with ancestral veneration. This creates bond among members.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 5

Notes: this applies to rite of passage for members during birth, puberty, marriage and death or during initiation rite.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 300

Notes: this take place during annual festival that entails prayer for the community at large.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 12

Notes: it takes a whole day or more in some cases

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: the use of spirit liquor is highly valuable in the traditional worship of the Yoruba people. it serves as medium of gratifying the request of members. It is also used for libation during sacrifice .

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: food like deer meat and soup made with jute leave are forbidden in this group religious worship.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: The male must plait their hair like female

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: This entail understanding of ritual language of bata drum known as ena bata (bata irony)

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence of principle of consanguinity relationship among members. This in Yoruba palance is called alajobi. It is a form of bond that connects both immediate and extended family together through blood and marriage.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: It is wide spread among other Yoruba tribes as this seems to clarify their total communal system.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Notes: Due to modernity, the family ties expressed now has made this system uncommon.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Oyo was first characterized as empire during the ancient period but recognized as part of Yoruba tribe. The city was established by Oranmiyan, a prince of Ife around fifteen century. The city was known for its warring expedition during the period Fulani jihadist were on war rampage of the Yoruba land. The empire of Oyo came to an end when Afonja , the war lord of the empire aligned with the Fulani but the step led to the destruction of oyo empire and the creation of many Yoruba city states like Ibadan, Ogbomosho, and Ede .

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government agency and community development. The local municipal gives opportunity to people in this regard.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: through the institution created by the government and non governmental agencies

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: This is based on family care and kinship relationship.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Institution like NOA (National Orientation agency) make available series of entrepreneurial opportunities.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: They have informal education from the background of family and religious ethics

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are state, federal and private institutions from primary to tertiary that cater for learning processes of members. Most of these institutions are sponsored by the government and civil societies

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Mostly this is done at home and in a conventional way in the school.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is isese community that cater for the affairs of indigenous religious outfit. All indigenous religious group are qualified to relate in this platform.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group interact with other institutional buraecracy majorly from economic and political background. The only challenge they have is that could not relate with major institution known as The Nigeria Inter-Religious Council(NIREC) due to religious bigotry.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Through their local farming scheme, they provide food and sell directly to the retailers. They keep and store farming products annually for disbursement and sale.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The scheme is much capital intensive for them to bear so they rely on government.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government, town planning agencies and civil societies

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Transportation are provided through joint entrepreneur association or cooperative company

that are independent of government.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is mandatory for group members to pay taxes for public development and other social services which government provides.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: There is community policing .Members are core agent in vigilante police group within this category in the community

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are consider to be a local vigilante under the control of an establish government police authority. They have no power of prosecution.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In case of capital punishment they are not left out because that is within official government jurisdiction

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This applies to grievous offences like murder

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: If actions contradict civil law such punishment can be upheld.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: in case property has been obtained through illegal activities. This process is used to combat crime and ensure justice is served.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Since they socialize and live in civil society, they are bound by the legal code of the government

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group have an organized vigilante operating as para military but approved by the government

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Notes: they are part of oodua vigilante group which is a community based army

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: yoruba language

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English and other foreign language are accepted for interaction apart from the local language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English language is officially adopted in school for learning

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They have informal calendar that is cultural but not written

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The listed are means of productions and of life sustenance during the ancient time. These methods are still present till this moment because members engaged purely in agricultural scheme

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Members engaged only on medium and small scale production.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Oladosu, Olusegun. "Drum Language of the Yoruba People". *Vinayasadhana: Dharmaram Journal of Psycho-spiritual Formation* VI, no. 1 (2015): 37-56.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Magesa, Laurenti. *African Religion: The Moral Traditions of Abundant Life*. Nairobi: Pauline Publication Africa, 1998.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Lugira, Aloysius . *World Religions: African Teaditional Religions*. New York: Chelsea House, 2009.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Salami, Ayo. *Yoruba Theology and Tradition: The Genealogy*. Lagos: NIDD Publishing Company, 2008.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Olajubu, Oludare. *Iwe Asa Bile Yoruba*. Lagos: Longman Nigeria, 1978.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Gehman, Richard . *African Traditional Religion :in the Light of the Bible*. Plateau: Acts, 2013.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Awolalu, Omosade , and Adelumo Dopamu. *West Africa Traditional Religion*. Ibadan: Macmillan, 2005.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Awolalu, Omosade. *Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites*. Hallow, Essex, UK: Longman, 1981.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Oladosu, Olusegun Adebolu. "Preservation of Yoruba Indigenous Drumming Heritage". *Yoruba Studies Review* 7, no. 2 (January 19, 2023): 1-20.
<https://doi.org/10.32473/ysr.7.2.132803>.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Oladosu, Olusegun. "Indigenous Drums and Aesthetic Symbols in Ecological Ritual of the Yoruba People". *Ife Journal of the Institute of Cultural Studies* 11 (2015): 113-32.

Reference: Sango Religious group in Oyo, Ajibade, Olusola. "Sango's Erindinlogun Divinatory System". In *Sango in Africa and the African in Diaspora*. Bloomington and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, 2009.